

Content Creation and Affiliate Marketing as a Side Hustle

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From casual online posting and sharing pictures and videos, the practice has now led me to earn money online through social media. It is called content creation, defined as the production and distribution of digital content on social media that informs, educates, or entertains. Affiliate marketing is an online income strategy that involves earning commissions from products or services through referral links. Both strategies help find a viable source of income through social media.

The profit I generate from these activities is very small, but it shows my commitment to learning and growth. My content can be seen across several platforms, including a Facebook page "LOLLY EV" dedicated to my Mini Electric Vehicle (EV), along with a YouTube channel "Mini EV Adventures" that features our experiences, stories, and travels. Additional personal content and advocacy materials are published through my Facebook and Instagram account "Mondirific Mina," while short-form content and video clips are shared on my TikTok page "mondirific." Through these channels, I advocate for financial and digital literacy and for promoting EVs as a sustainable mode of transportation.

Becoming popular and earning substantially through affiliate marketing and content creation takes time. Sometimes it is hard to stay consistent and patient, given the minimal level of interaction and turtle-like progress. I continue doing this because even well-known influencers today humbly started from scratch.

This journey made me realize that both content creation and affiliate marketing require significant time, patience, and effort. Even if the financial returns are not that big, the experience itself has been a valuable learning that enhanced my communication skills and creativity in this digital era.

This type of side hustle humbled me and taught me a valuable lesson that indeed "Progress is gradual". Small but consistent efforts can eventually pile up into meaningful results. Each post, video, and shared content represents a humble step toward establishing both influence and long-term income potential.

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